

D1.6

Data Management Plan Final Version

PoDIUM

PDI connectivity and cooperation enablers building trust and sustainability for CCAM

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Table of contents

Contributors.....	2
Quality Control.....	2
Version History	2
Legal Disclaimer	2
List of tables.....	6
List of abbreviations and acronyms.....	7
Executive Summary	8
1. Introduction	9
1.1. Project intro.....	9
1.2. Purpose of the deliverable	9
1.3. Intended audience.....	10
1.4. Document structure	10
2. Data summary.....	11
2.1. Technical data.....	11
2.2. User questionnaire data	13
2.3. Evaluation data.....	13
2.4. Internal administrative data.....	14
2.5. Data on project outcomes and studies	14
3. FAIR data.....	15
3.1. Technical data.....	15
3.2. User questionnaire data	16
3.3. Evaluation data.....	17
3.4. Internal administrative data.....	17
3.5. Data on project outcomes and studies	17
4. Data protection and ethical aspects	19
4.1. Surveys Among Participants	19
4.2. Participants Enrolled in Project Studies	19
4.3. Camera Data.....	19
5. Data security	21
5.1. Data security requirements.....	21
5.2. Secure data storage implementation.....	21
6. Other research outputs	23
7. Allocation of resources.....	24

8. Conclusion and summary 25

References 26

List of tables

Table 1: Overview of technical data subcategories	12
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List of abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
API	Application Programming Interface
CAM	Cooperative Awareness Message
CCAM	Connected, Cooperative and Automated Mobility
CC BY	Creative Commons Attribution International Public License
CC 0	Creative Common Public Domain Dedication
C-ITS	Cooperative Intelligent Transportation System
CPM	Collective Perception Message
DENM	Decentralised Environmental Notification Messages
D	Deliverable
DMP	Data Management Plan
DMPO	Data Management and Protection Officer
DT	Digital Twin
EC	European Commission
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reuseable
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
ICCS	Institute of Communication and Computer Systems
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
ISO	International Organisation for Standardisation
IVIM	Infrastructure to Vehicle Information Message
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LIDAR	Light Detection and Ranging
LL	Living Lab
M	Month
MCM	Manoeuvre Coordination Message
MEC	Multi-access Edge Computing
PCAP	Packet Capture
PU	Public
RSU	Roadside Unit
T	Task
UC	Use Case
VAM	VRU Awareness Message
VRU	Vulnerable Road User
WP	Work Package
XML	Extensible Markup Language

Executive Summary

This deliverable is the third and final version of the Data Management Plan for the project PoDIUM – PDI connectivity and cooperation enablers building trust and sustainability for Connected, Cooperative and Automated Mobility (CCAM). The Data Management Plan presents guidelines including the description of the data, procedures for data management and data management tools for accessing and using the PoDIUM data for research purposes with the state of information at Month (M) 39 of the project.

PoDIUM generates and handles different types of data in the following categories: Technical data, user questionnaire data, evaluation data, internal administrative data, and data on project outcomes and studies. These data types differ in their purpose and how they are handled. Stored technical data, user acceptance data, evaluation data and data on project outcomes and studies are made available as open as possible, provided this does not conflict with legal obligations, commercial interests, or partners' intellectual property rights (IPRs), and remains fully compliant with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Internal administrative data is internal working material and is not made available beyond the consortium. The principles of making data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR) are applied in the project. There are differences among the data categories in terms of how FAIR principles are applied, which are described in the document.

This document collects and describes the results of Work Package 1 – “Project Management”, Task 1.3 – “Data Management Plan” and fulfils the requirements for D1.6 – “Data Management Final Version”. It is primarily intended to serve as a comprehensive internal guideline and reference for all PoDIUM beneficiaries. It is formulated based on the requirements in the Grant Agreement and, together with the Grant Agreement, serves as the foundational reference for all data management activities within PoDIUM, in close cooperation with the Living Labs. All project partners are responsible for collecting, managing and sharing data according to the guidelines and procedures detailed in the DMP.

1. Introduction

1.1. Project intro

PoDIUM aims to support advanced Use Cases (UC) of CCAM in real traffic conditions. Building on the proposed urban and highway UCs in the facilities of 3 well-equipped Living Labs (LLs) in Germany, Italy and Spain, PoDIUM addresses a comprehensive range of requirements for availability and performance of connectivity as well as the different cooperation enablers per UC. The proposed UCs aim to advance a set of key technologies both within the physical and digital components of mobility infrastructure. In particular, the following non-exhaustive list of contributions are pursued:

- A multi-connectivity approach to ensure reliability, availability and redundancy of the Physical and Digital Infrastructure (PDI) system.
- Advanced data fusion and integration of Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) to the proposed hybrid data management environment to enable enhanced environment perception models towards digital twins.
- New Cooperative Intelligent Transport Systems (C-ITS) messages for enabling the specific advanced CCAM UCs.
- Ensure software integrity, trust and truthfulness of CCAM data, their exchange and their processing.
- Demonstration of urban and highway UCs in a diverse set of configurations with the integration of Vulnerable Road Users (VRUs).

1.2. Purpose of the deliverable

This Data Management Plan provides a complete set of guidelines including the description of the data and data management tools for accessing and using the PoDIUM data for research purposes.

The Data management Plan (DMP) has been elaborated as part of T1.3 – “Data Management Plan” of WP1 – “Project management” and defines procedures on how to handle personal data to guarantee citizens’ fundamental rights and avoid misuse of the project results. It specifies how the data is stored securely and whether it is deleted after the end of the project or archived for further use by the research community. In the latter case, the DMP contains recommendations for guaranteeing future access to the data by consortium partners and external parties.

Following the procedures, guidelines and requirements defined in the DMP ensures that data is made Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR). The principle is to be as open as possible and to make all data available. Exceptions are outlined for data that cannot be made available due to technical, legal, or ethical constraints. Such data are those that may not be shared due to legal requirements or because they conflict with the commercial interests and intellectual property rights of the partners.

The DMP further addresses data privacy and security considerations, detailing the corresponding requirements and applicable standards. The DMP complies with EU and international regulations on the management and use of data and is harmonised with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

This deliverable constitutes the third and final version of the Data Management Plan and integrates all developments and findings made throughout the project.

1.3. Intended audience

The dissemination level of D1.6 is 'public' (PU) and thus, the deliverable is available not only to members of the consortium and the European Commission (EC) Services but also those outside the project. This document is primarily intended to serve as an internal guideline and reference for all PoDIUM beneficiaries, especially the governance bodies such as the General Assembly and the Technical Management Team.

1.4. Document structure

The structure of this deliverable is as follows:

- Chapter 2 – Data summary: Provides a description of the types of data generated by the project and specifies information about the data types.
- Chapter 3 – FAIR data: Describes how data is made findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable.
- Chapter 4 – Data protection and ethical aspects: Details the methodology to be followed to reach compliance with data protection regulation and consideration of ethical aspects.
- Chapter 5 – Data security: Describes the approach towards guaranteeing data security.
- Chapter 6 – Other research outputs: Describes management of other research outputs.
- Chapter 7 – Allocation of resources: Describes how allocation of required resources for data management is implemented.
- Chapter 8 – Conclusion: Summarises the key elements of the deliverable.

2. Data summary

PoDIUM generates and handles different types of data which can be organised into the following main categories:

- **Technical data:** generated by the PoDIUM systems.
- **User questionnaire data:** collected through user acceptance questionnaires among UC demonstration participants.
- **Evaluation data:** comprises measurements of the performance indicators and the results presented in the outcomes and scientific publications.
- **Internal administrative data:** data generated/shared internally for administrative and management purposes.
- **Data on project outcomes and studies:** data generated from managerial, technical and scientific activities for reporting project achievements.

No existing data are reused. The data used in PoDIUM are fully generated within the project. The individual data categories are described in detail in the following subsections.

2.1. Technical data

Technical data includes all data generated by the PoDIUM system during development, operation, or testing, such as sensor data, processed data, and communication data. Table 1 provides a description and examples of data for each category of technical data. In PoDIUM, the exchange of technical data between vehicles and infrastructure mainly takes place in the form of C-ITS messages. These messages are therefore listed separately as communication data. C-ITS message types include the Cooperative Awareness Message (CAM), Collective Perception Message (CPM), Decentralised Environmental Notification Message (DENM), Infrastructure to Vehicle Information Message (IVIM), Manoeuvre Coordination Message (MCM) and Vulnerable Road User Awareness Message (VAM). A detailed description of the technical data logged in each of the PoDIUM LLs, separated by the specificities and needs of each UC, can be found in D4.1 – “Deployment of PoDIUM architecture to the LLs and development of data collection tools”.

The systems deployed in this project, including sensors and components within connected and automated vehicles, generate a significant volume of data. However, only data essential for PoDIUM specific activities in the areas of development and validation is retained and made available, while operational data not relevant to research objectives, such as non-critical vehicle data, is excluded from storage and disclosure. It is therefore not detailed in the DMP. Chapter 3.1 sets out in detail the conditions under which the disclosure of technical data is not considered required.

Table 1: Overview of technical data subcategories

Technical data subcategories	Description of data	Example	Data provision format
Sensor data	Data collected by various types of sensors – either embedded in infrastructure elements or installed in vehicles.	UC 3: Camera feed UC 4: Light detection and ranging (LiDAR)	In the systems used in PoDIUM, various sensor data is generated. Sensor data is provided in the form of CSV or JSON files. Sensor data collected by cameras is made available in the form of MP4s. To exchange and process sensor data, C-ITS messages are often used: Position data is exchanged in the form of CAM, VAMs or DENMs, and environmental information via CPMs. A description of how C-ITS messages are provided can be found separately in the table.
Processed data	Data resulting from the fusion and processing of sensor and other input data. ¹	UC 2: The TMC processes the CAMs received from the vehicles into traffic metrics.	Processed data is mainly provided in the form of CSV and JSON files. Like sensor data, processed data is often exchanged in the form of C-ITS messages within PoDIUM.
Communication data	Communication data includes metadata and message content that reflect the quality and performance of links between vehicles and the MEC, transmitted via different communication technologies. C-ITS messages as a subcategory of communication data are described separately below.	UC 1: Data like the processing time of the cooperative manoeuvre planning and the communication delay to the digital twin.	Communication data is provided in various formats depending on the content type: JSON (e.g., delay metrics), PCAP (e.g., raw data packets), CSV (e.g., beacon messages), and TXT (e.g., request logs).
Communication data: C-ITS data	In the UCs, a collection of C-ITS messages, including CAM, DENM, IVIM, VAM, CPM and MCM, facilitates the exchange of information between infrastructure and road users, encompassing both vehicles and VRUs.	UC 2: Infrastructure informs connected vehicles about the presence of an emergency vehicle through DENMs.	The data from messages is provided in various formats, including PCAP for standardised messages and JSON or XML for PoDIUM-extended messages. Standards for the C-ITS messages and protocols are detailed in D3.3 – “Final report on the PoDIUM platform development”.

¹Please note: Only data that is utilised in the final output is being considered.

2.2. User questionnaire data

The evaluation of public acceptance of the PoDIUM platform, together with the UCs implemented in the three LLs, is carried out using impact assessment and user acceptance surveys based on structured questionnaires. For each UC, two complementary survey tools have been developed: On-site questionnaires, addressed to participants who directly engaged in the PoDIUM demonstrations (e.g., drivers, vulnerable road users, operators, and observers) and online questionnaires, distributed shortly after the demonstrations to reach a wider group of stakeholders, including public authorities, industry actors, and members of the general public. The questionnaires combined multiple-choice questions to identify user profiles and interaction contexts, with five-point Likert scale statements (1 = Strongly disagree to 5 = Strongly agree).

The surveys cover four main sections:

- Demographics and mobility background: collecting information on age, gender, user category, mobility role, and prior exposure to CCAM or C-ITS technologies.
- Interaction context: recording the specific UC experienced, the respondent's role (e.g., driver, VRU, observer, operator), and the demonstration environment (urban or highway).
- Perceptions and acceptance: Likert-scale statements covering core dimensions such as Intention to Use, Perceived Ease of Use, Perceived Usefulness, Trust, Reliability, Privacy, and Social Norms.
- Behavioural intention and willingness to adopt: assessing respondents' readiness to use PoDIUM-enabled services in future everyday mobility scenarios.

The objective was to gather around 100 valid responses across the three Living Labs. This sample size was deemed adequate for descriptive analyses and comparisons between sites. The collected questionnaire data, together with details on sampling approaches, representativeness, and survey instruments, are documented in D5.3 – “Public acceptance and impact assessment report”.

2.3. Evaluation data

This category contains all data from the project's evaluation tasks, drawing on technical and user questionnaire data as input. It is the result of the evaluation of the UCs and new services resulting from the project. The data used for evaluation is therefore a subset of the data generated during the lifecycle of the project and is produced in the evaluation tasks defined in WP5 (T5.1, 5.2 and 5.3). More specifically, data is collected from (end-user-) equipment and the monitoring mechanisms following the experimentation procedures.

The evaluation is split into two parts: technical evaluation and user acceptance evaluation. Evaluation is mostly conducted by using Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), which help assess the effectiveness and impact of the various project outcomes.

Data on the assessment of performance metrics and especially KPI measures are of particular interest for the whole community – and are at the same time crucial for the implemented solutions to become market ready. The process for defining the evaluation data involves careful consideration and collaboration among project partners to ensure that the selected evaluation metrics align closely with project objectives. KPIs have been defined both for the PoDIUM platform as well as for each individual UC.

For the technical evaluation of the PoDIUM platform, KPIs cover service availability, latency, reliability, data security, and the performance of the integrity architecture. In contrast, the individual use cases focus on evaluating the overall effectiveness and accuracy of the solutions developed for each UC. The following Deliverables provide detailed information on the evaluation data:

- D2.3 – “PoDIUM availability and cooperation enablers definition and evaluation data specifications” outlines the technical KPIs, explains the procedures for collecting evaluation data during testing, and describes how these data are used to derive the KPIs. It also defines the user-acceptance metrics, covering intention to use, perceived usefulness, ease of use, trust, reliability, and privacy.
- D5.1 – “PoDIUM evaluation methodology” details the overall evaluation approach for the project, encompassing both the technical assessment of the PoDIUM platform and use cases as well as the user-acceptance evaluation, and provides updated definitions for the technical KPIs.
- D5.2 – “Technical evaluation and demonstration of the UCs” documents the data-collection processes for the technical evaluation, and the resulting KPI values.
- Likewise, D5.3 – “Public acceptance and impact assessment report” presents the collected data along with the KPIs of the public acceptance and impact assessment.

A description of the technical and user questionnaire data from which the evaluation data are derived are given in the individual chapters.

2.4. Internal administrative data

This data type refers to data produced by project management activities, such as meeting minutes, recordings, internal reports, or other data stored. It is collected by the management team, which includes the project manager, the WP- and task-leaders. D1.1 – “Project Management Plan” – provides a description of internal administrative data collected.

2.5. Data on project outcomes and studies

Data in this category is generated within the project for the purpose of reporting project outcomes from managerial, technical and scientific activities. This includes project deliverables, scientific and technical publications, videos for demonstration and presentations. Such data may be useful, e.g., for potential future projects, which build on the work of PoDIUM as well as the industry and public bodies wanting to learn from PoDIUM outcomes. All the data within this category is provided in text format or graphical representation. D7.9 – “Report on the dissemination activities” details the data produced for disseminating project outcomes.

3. FAIR data

Since the PoDIUM project is an EU-funded project, the FAIR data principles must be followed. The FAIR principles are defined as follows:

1. **Findable:** Data and metadata should be easy to locate for both humans and machines. This requires the use of machine-readable metadata to enable the automated discovery of datasets and related services.
2. **Accessible:** Users must be able to understand how it can be accessed – this may involve authentication and authorisation mechanisms where necessary.
3. **Interoperable:** Data should be compatible with other datasets and systems. This includes the ability to integrate with applications, workflows, and tools for analysis, storage, and processing.
4. **Reusable:** Data and metadata must be thoroughly described, enabling replication, integration, and application in various contexts.

The objective of applying the FAIR principles is to facilitate data sharing and reuse of data, also in the long term, thereby maximising the impact of research.² While FAIR promotes openness to increase scientific and societal value, it also acknowledges the need for appropriate restrictions when necessary. The principle is to be as open as possible and to provide all data, except those which are conflicting with the law or commercial interests and IPRs of partners (‘as open as possible, as closed as necessary’).

Due to the specific characteristics of the different data categories as outlined in Chapter 2, the application of the FAIR principles varies across these categories. Therefore, this chapter presents the application of the FAIR principles in separate sections for each data category, specifying the conditions under which the principles apply and outlining any exceptions.

3.1. Technical data

To make the technical data findable, D5.2 – “Technical evaluation and demonstration of the UCs” provides the direct link for each dataset made openly available. As preferred repository for open data, Zenodo has been selected. Zenodo is a general-purpose open access repository developed under the European OpenAIRE program and operated by CERN.

Further, findability within Zenodo is ensured by adhering to a set of structured guidelines: A specific repository within Zenodo, titled “Open Repository for EU Funded Research,” has been created.³ Within this repository, each Use Case provides its datasets in a single main folder named PoDIUM-Dataset-UCx-2025, which is also available as a compressed file (PoDIUM-Dataset-UCx-2025.zip). This folder contains all related dataset subfolders and a README.txt file including key metadata such as author(s), dataset description, publication date, license (by default, Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International), any embargo period, and funding information (PoDIUM: PDI connectivity and cooperation enablers building trust and sustainability for CCAM. Project No. 101069547. Call HORIZON-CL5-2021-D6-01, European Union). To each dataset uploaded to Zenodo a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) is automatically assigned, ensuring persistent and citable access.

² A detailed description of the FAIR by OpenAIRE can be found under this link: <https://www.openaire.eu/how-to-make-your-data-fair>

³ The Zenodo repository can be found under this link: https://zenodo.org/communities/podium_project/about

All technical data made to be openly accessible as well as how accessibility is ensured is described in D4.1 – “Deployment of PoDIUM architecture to the LLS and development of data collection tools”. A framework for defining data collection and storage has been established and includes the following steps:

- Identification of the data relevant for logging, including the purpose and format of the data
- Definition of the logging scheme and format
- Definition of storage and APIs

Some technical data is not shared for the following reason: The systems deployed in this project, including sensors and components within automated vehicles, generate a significant volume of data. Storing and sharing this data would result in a disproportionate burden in terms of volume and management effort, without providing added value to the project objectives. Therefore, such non-critical or redundant data is not made accessible. The same applies to pre-demo test data, as the finalised test data sufficiently covers the relevant results and findings.

Technical data is made interoperable by using standardised data formats as outlined in D4.1. Regarding C-ITS messages in specific, C-ITS interoperability is an important element of PoDIUM as this is key to facilitate the interaction between infrastructure and vehicle side. The basis for CCAM research at the data level is the use of C-ITS messages. These are standardised by the International Organisation for Standardisation (ISO) and the European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI). The respective communication profiles are openly available and published at infrastructure and at vehicle level. C-ITS messages are therefore used in PoDIUM. PoDIUM is fully aligned with the C-ROADS approach.⁴ This ensures interoperability and the correct interpretation of data. References to the relevant standards of the C-ITS messages are included in the metadata to support proper interpretation and reuse.

Furthermore, any additional developments of the project build as much as possible on standardised elements. The potential extension of C-ITS messages, such as MCM, CPM and VAM are made available via D3.3 – “Final report on the PoDIUM platform evaluation” as well as technical papers. They are also used as input to standardisation activities (in certain cases, due to copyright issues, only references to the changes to the standards are published). Due to copyright issues some technical/scientific papers may instead be published via institutional repositories, which also follow the FAIR principles. Proposing only additions to already standardised messages shall guarantee as much interoperability and reusability as possible. All technical data provided is free to reuse.

3.2. User questionnaire data

All data collected from user questionnaire responses from pilots are made Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable with the clarification that any personal information of the user is removed before publication.

The methodology for making pilot user questionnaire data FAIR-compliant is defined in D5.3 – “Public acceptance and impact assessment report”. This public deliverable presents the corresponding results for each UC in the relevant sections.

⁴ More information on C-Roads, a joint initiative of European Member States and road operators for testing and implementing C-ITS services, can be found under this link: <https://www.c-roads.eu/platform.html>

3.3. Evaluation data

All technical KPI results are made findable and accessible through D5.2 – “Technical Evaluation and Demonstration of the UCs”, and the resulting KPIs for user acceptance are documented in D5.3 – “Public Acceptance and Impact Assessment Report”.

As the evaluation data are ultimately derived from both technical data and user questionnaire data, the linkage between these input data types and the resulting KPIs is ensured as follows: for KPIs based on technical data, direct references to the corresponding datasets in the PoDIUM Zenodo repository are provided in D5.2, while user questionnaire data are reported directly in D5.3.

How FAIR principles are applied to technical evaluation and user questionnaire data used as input for evaluation in specific, is outlined in the chapters on technical data and user questionnaire data.

3.4. Internal administrative data

Internal administrative data is accessible to all project partners. Beyond this, FAIR criteria do not apply to internal administrative data. Data is stored and shared between project partners by using a project management tool, which requires the authentication of the users (Redmine hosted by the project coordinator).

3.5. Data on project outcomes and studies

All project deliverables, with the exception of the deliverables on business models (D6.2 – “Business models for sustainable CCAM service provisioning” and D6.3 – “Techno-economic analysis and sustainability of PoDIUM business models”), exploitation plans (D7.7 and D7.8) and the exploitation report (D7.11) are made publicly available via the PoDIUM website and the EC portal. Public deliverables may be freely reused without limitation. The excluded deliverables remain confidential to protect commercially sensitive information and partner interests. They are classified as sensitive.

Documentation of developments (text or graphical representations such as presentations & videos from public events and conferences) are made publicly available (as far as contractually permitted) and shared via the PoDIUM Website.

Research publications are made publicly available, given the publishing body copyright agreement, in a machine-readable electronic copy with open access, at the latest upon publication, and deposited in trusted repositories listed in OpenAIRE (Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe), namely Zenodo, and/or institutional repositories of project partners as well as the PoDIUM website. As described before, on Zenodo, a specific repository within Zenodo, titled “Open Repository for EU Funded Research,” has been created.

Due to copyright issues some technical/scientific papers may instead be published via institutional repositories, which also follow FAIR principles. PoDIUM consortium partners are free to choose between self-archiving (“green” Open Access) and open access publishing (“gold” Open access).

The following information is to be included as metadata for scientific publications: author(s) and if applicable their organisation, title, publication date, publication venue, funding information (PoDIUM: PDI connectivity and cooperation enablers building trust and sustainability for CCAM. Project No. 101069547. Call HORIZON-CL5-2021-D6-01, European Union), and license. All materials produced are, by default, licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license (CC BY 4.0), allowing others to freely use, share, and adapt the content with appropriate credit. For monographs and other long-form text publications, more restrictive licenses such as CC BY-NC (non-commercial use) or CC BY-ND (no derivatives) may be applied to protect the integrity of the work and prevent

commercial exploitation. The metadata of all scientific publications remain fully open and are released under the Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication (CC0) or an equivalent license, ensuring unrestricted reuse and interoperability across research repositories. Any project-generated data used in a scientific publication must include a reference or link to the repository where the data can be accessed. A persistent identifier must be assigned to all publications. This is ensured through Zenodo or the institutional repositories of the project partners, guaranteeing persistent and citable access. Information on all research outputs, tools, and instruments required to validate the conclusions of the scientific publications are likewise made available through the respective repository.

4. Data protection and ethical aspects

This section describes data protection and ethical aspects and details the methodology to be followed to reach compliance with data protection regulation and consideration of ethical aspects.

The project activities adhere to the Helsinki Declaration and the Ethics of Information and Communication Technologies report (2012) from the European Group on Ethics in Science and New Technologies to the EC and conform to the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the EU. All the data processing activities comply with the requirements of GDPR, as described in the Grant Agreement (chapter 15.2 - Data processing by the beneficiaries).

Within PoDIUM several GDPR critical data is collected and processed. The application of the GDPR principles is described in the following identified sensitive data categories. The approach of PoDIUM prioritises data minimisation, security, and respects individuals' rights while enabling the legitimate research and operational needs of the project.

4.1. Surveys Among Participants

Within PoDIUM, user acceptance surveys are conducted among participants in the UC demonstrations. To comply with the GDPR, these surveys are anonymous and do not collect any personal data from the participants, but only information related to their opinions and attitudes towards the use of the proposed demonstrated services and towards CCAM in general. User acceptance questionnaires are collected only locally by the local Living Lab partners and only anonymised data is exploited at project level. The data to be processed is relevant and limited to the purposes of the project (in accordance with the “data minimisation” principle). According to the objectives and methodology of PoDIUM there are no ethical concerns arising from the implementation and execution of the project since no personal data are required in the user acceptance part or the evaluation and demonstration phases.

4.2. Participants Enrolled in Project Studies

Participants enrolled within the project's studies provided informed consent and signed an age and language appropriate consent prior to each new study/demonstration. The participants do not include potentially vulnerable groups, minors or any other persons who are unable to give informed consent. The completed informed consent forms and information sheets (explaining the scope in language and terms intelligible to the participants) are kept on file. Participants are also provided with clear opportunities to provide feedback regarding their participation. The informed consent form collects only essential personal information, specifically the participant's first and last names and, if necessary, their age.

4.3. Camera Data

For testing, validation, and demonstration, video data is collected within the UCs. Camera footage on public roads that captures vehicle number plates and identifiable individuals clearly qualifies as personal data under GDPR. Within the UCs, partners operating roadside cameras have signed formal agreements with the respective municipal councils, confirming legal, contractual and technical compliance with all GDPR and data protection guidelines. Conformity with data protection and security requirements is therefore ensured through these signed agreements and the implemented technical

and organisational measures. Further information on the installation of the cameras is given in D4.2 – “PoDIUM LLS Integration and Pre-evaluation Testing Report.”

5. Data security

The PoDIUM consortium is aware of the significant potential risks related to data security, in particular during data collection and exchange. Among others, these have been integrated in the risk assessment performed at the beginning (M03) of the project, specifically identified in D1.2 – “Quality Assurance and Risk Management”.

Cybersecurity and privacy principles are applied to all data categories. Therefore, general methodologies and principles concerning end users are set up. Involvement of end-users in test activities are carried out in a responsible way by providing a briefing on the project and the test activities, including information about potential risks.

This chapter provides a summary of the data collection and data storage guidelines established within the project.

5.1. Data security requirements

The following security principles are defined to achieve protection against any type of modification:

- **Authentication:** Users accessing data servers must undergo authentication processes to verify their identity. Additionally, the servers themselves must undergo authentication to ensure their legitimacy and integrity within the network.
- **Authorisation:** Access to data servers is restricted to authenticated and authorised users. User categories and their respective rights are predefined and enforced to ensure only authorised users have access. Access control mechanisms are identified for each trial site and project-wide to enforce authorisation protocols effectively.
- **Accounting:** Comprehensive logging of all user access and modifications to resources is essential for accountability. Secure logs prevent users from denying their actions, ensuring accountability for any accessed, altered, or deleted data files.
- **Confidentiality:** Data stored on servers must be encrypted during transmission and storage to protect against unauthorised access. Encryption ensures that even if data is intercepted, it remains secure and confidential.
- **Communication Security:** Access to servers should occur via encrypted communication channels, such as HTTPS, to prevent eavesdropping and ensure the integrity of data in transit. Encrypted channels provide an added layer of security against data interception and manipulation.
- **Availability:** Security measures must guarantee that data on servers remains available to authorised users throughout the defined service period. Regular backups of data ensure data availability and integrity, allowing for swift recovery in the event of data loss or corruption

5.2. Secure data storage implementation

Public data is stored on Zenodo, where appropriate security measures are ensured through the platform’s protocols. For technical data in specific, a detailed description outlining comprehensive technical guidelines for data management is provided in D4.1 – “Deployment of PoDIUM architecture to the LLs and development of data collection tools”. These include the guidelines for data collection, transmission, preprocessing, protection and storage.

Other internal data generated during the project is securely stored locally on the servers of each partner involved in data collection and generation. Any user questionnaire response (only anonymised

data) from the demonstration events is stored and regularly backed up through the internal collaboration tool 'Redmine'. The Institute of Communication and Computer Systems (ICCS) is hosting a Redmine installation, where a dedicated project area has been created for PoDIUM. The web access is secured using a digital certificate from TERENA. The server hosting the Redmine installation is located in the ICCS premises in Athens, Greece, in a secured rack in the ICCS server room. The server databases are backed up daily, while its files are backed up every second day. The server is built with multiple redundancies, network and disk-wise, in order to ensure its constant operation and network access. Third-party services like Dropbox and Google Drive are not to be used for sensitive data storage and sharing.

During the project, data is shared among partners as determined appropriate by the partners themselves. Potentially sensitive data is only stored locally in conformance with GDPR, the consortium agreement and the internal consortium procedures as specified in D1.1 – “Project management plan” and D1.2 – “Quality Management Plan”.

Data that is produced during the runtime of the PoDIUM project is stored in local and central servers during the duration of the whole project. It is treated as confidential and security processes and techniques are applied to ensure their confidentiality in compliance with the regulation on the protection of private data (GDPR).

6. Other research outputs

This section describes the management of other research outputs, as outlined in the Horizon Europe DMP template and Annex 5 of the Grant Agreement. Other research outputs include engineered results and processes such as software, algorithms, protocols, models, workflows, and electronic notebooks.

Project partners either use open-source code and implement standard-based solutions in their deliverables or aim to contribute project outputs to open-source communities and standard specifications. Details on open-source code use and standard contributions are addressed in the CA. Extensions made to the C-ITS messages and protocols within PoDIUM are detailed in D3.3 – “Final report on the PoDIUM platform development”. While the project aims to make results available as open-source technologies where possible, the consortium recognises that certain challenges may justify exceptions. These include:

- IPR protection for outputs with commercial potential
- Safeguarding background IPR and know-how
- Avoiding negative impacts on partners’ market positions

Final guidelines on IPR management, as well as the identified IP, are documented in D7.11 – “Exploitation Report”.

7. Allocation of resources

The data used in PoDIUM are generated and collected as part of the project activities in the UCs. Task 1.3 is dedicated to data management and is led by AustriaTech, who is also the Data Management and Protection Officer (DMPO) of the project. The DMPO coordinates the Data Management Plan and raises potential issues and proposes solutions for dealing adequately with data privacy and data protection regulations and liaises with the partners who perform the trials to establish procedures that ensure the proper application of the data protection policies. The DMPO is responsible for defining procedures to ensure that data is managed following FAIR principles, in a secure and GDPR compliant way. PoDIUM partners are responsible for collecting, managing and sharing data according to the guidelines and procedures detailed in the DMP.

Budget allocated under Task 7.2 of the project supports the production and publication of scientific and technical publications. For long-term preservation of data, the data is stored on Zenodo, which is operated by CERN and free of charge. PoDIUM partners have not made use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management.

8. Conclusion and summary

The final PoDIUM Data Management Plan sets out a comprehensive framework for managing the project's diverse data, aligned with the status at the end of the project (M39). It focuses on various data types, including technical, evaluation, user questionnaire, and project outcome data. The plan is designed to adhere to FAIR principles, i.e. ensuring data is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable while also defining justified exceptions. Moreover, stringent measures are in place to uphold data privacy in accordance with GDPR regulations, ensuring anonymity and obtaining informed consent for user participation. Data security is also a top priority, with robust measures implemented to safeguard data throughout its lifecycle. By promoting responsible data handling practices and facilitating data sharing, the PoDIUM Data Management Plan not only supports the project's goals but also lays a foundation for future research in Connected, Cooperative and Automated Mobility.

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